

INTEGRATING OF MATHEMATICS IN SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Mathematical techniques play a significant role in developing and solving problems let it be theoretical or practical in the fields of science, management and technology. In spite of its importance these connections have not been acknowledged with much attention by the scholars. Mathematics Scholars often use the phrase that the spirit of this subject is in the beauty of numbers, figures and relations and it does hold true. Through this paper we lay emphasis on the relation of mathematics with the above-mentioned areas.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mathematics isn't subject field, neither is it accountancy; neither is it restricted to arithmetic. Pseudo arithmetic could be a sort of mathematics-like activity undertaken outside world, and sometimes by mathematicians themselves. It typically consists of determined attacks on noted queries, consisting of proof-attempts created in Associate with Science. The link to typically accepted arithmetic is analogous to it between fallacy and real science. *Srinivasa Ramanuja said "Mathematics is the science that deals with the logic of shape, quantity and arrangement"*.

Application of Mathematics:

- Statistics
- Numerical Analysis
- Business arithmetic

- Mathematical economic science

Mathematics play an important role in business to take decisions in the process of managerial decision models and algorithms. To turn to the specific aspects of the quantitative decision-making process, it is possible to recognize three distinct phases in every decision situation.

- Define the problem
- Formatting a model related to concept
- Select the suitable quantitative model to find a solution
- Apply an algorithm for mathematical operations that lead to a solution

The entire process is shown below:

II. ROLE OF MATHEMATICS IN BUSINESS STUDIES

Mathematics is one such subject that is used in almost all aspects of daily life. Most of the top-rated jobs across the world need a solid understanding of basic mathematics and some also require detailed knowledge of the subject. It plays a vital role in business like helps in maintaining records and managing business operations. The typical form of mathematics that is used in commerce includes the elementary arithmetic like fractions, decimals, probability etc. It also includes study of other topics like matrix algebra, linear programming, probability theory to understand business concepts easily. With the help of more advanced mathematics business management can be made more effective. Commercial

organisations have been and are using mathematics for accounting, managing inventory, sales, marketing and also analysis.

Application of Mathematics in business

- finding out variety patterns
- Calculate Production prices
- live Profits
- Manipulate numbers
- verify valuation
- Analyze Finances

Table: 1 (Products supplied by shoes companies)

Name of Shoes Companies	Products Supplied
NIKE	5000
ADDIDAS	4000
ASICS	1000
LIBERTY	2000
PUMA	2000
BATA	7000
RELAXO	1500
REEBOK	3000
CAMPUS	2500

Figure:1(Bar Graph of table 1)

III. ROLE OF MATHEMATICS IN TECHNOLOGY

We have often heard about the relation between technology and science but the relation between technology and mathematics is less discussed. Buddies are also related to each other in several ways. This relation is a two-edged sportswear technology is dependent on mathematics and so does mathematics on technology. Mathematics is much needed in modern technology such as the concept of proportion adopted in the modern era. The earliest use of mathematics is believed to be involved in the field of weaving. We need geometrical knowledge on daily basis such as for construction works, identifying various directions and many more. Compass is one such invention which has helped us over years and various modifications in basic designs of compass has helped us to cope up with time such as now a compass in our mobiles has been developed with the help of technology.

IV. ROLE OF MATHEMATICS IN ECONOMICS

Mathematical political economy depends on shaping all the relevant assumptions, conditions, and causative structures of economic theories in mathematical terms. There are two main edges from doing this. First, it permits economic theorists to use mathematical tools like pure mathematics and calculus to explain economic phenomena and draw precise inferences from their basic assumptions and

definitions. Second, it permits economists to operationalize these theories and inferences in order that they'll be tested through empirical observation exploitation quantitative knowledge and, if valid, accustomed manufacture quantitative predictions regarding economic matters for the advantage of businesses, investors, and policymakers. At that point, mathematical formulas are used to quantify changes within the economy. Mathematical political economy is the one that depends on quantitative strategies to support economic phenomena. arithmetic permits economists to exactly outline and check economic theories against universe knowledge.

Mathematics is an indispensable part of economics. It allows the economists to intricately construct models and derive conclusions from them with the help of mathematical logics. Economics also includes statistical analysis of data which is done with the help of mathematics. Mathematics has been increasingly important for the expression and communication of ideas in economics. Economics also includes a great deal of financial activities which are governed by mathematical models. The subject of accountancy also uses mathematics to interpret facts and figures. This subject also needs some basic and intermediate knowledge of mathematical concepts and theories. Mathematical formulas are used here to calculate and create charts and graphs for the interpretation of data. It is also used to evaluate transactions and for the overall work and supervision. Therefore, mathematical skills are important for the reality check in business studies.

Application of Mathematics in economic science:

- Quantitative ways are mathematical or applied math calculations that give economists with indicators for comparison this economic analysis to those of previous periods.
- Economists typically use numerous kinds of maths to make sure their personal judgments, inferences or theories are supported by meaning calculations.

Table: 2 (Demand Schedule)

Cost of the item	Quantity demanded of the item
Rs. 10	10
Rs. 30	8
Rs. 40	8
Rs. 50	10
Rs. 70	3

Table: 3 (Supply Schedule Table)

Cost	Quantity supplied of the item
Rs. 10	4
Rs. 30	5
Rs. 40	8
Rs. 50	10
Rs. 70	13

We plot these points on a graph and connect the points, the line is associated upward sloping line or curve and is termed the Individual supply curve for a specific item. The point at that the demand and curve of supply intercepts is termed the point of Equilibrium – it's that level of cost at that the quantity demanded and supplied is that the same. Watching the tables, you'll observe, it's at of Rs.4 that a quantity of eight is supplied and demanded and therefore is that the equilibrium cost and quantity for the item.

Figure 2. Graph of Individual demand and supply curves

V. ROLE OF MATHEMATICS IN SCIENCE

Chemists use maths for a spread of tasks. They balance the equation of a reaction, use mathematical calculations that square measure fully necessary to explore vital ideas in chemistry, and utilize dimensional analysis to search out any vary of knowledge regarding reactions from finding the mass of chemicals reacted to the concentration of a chemical in a very answer. maths is additionally accustomed calculate energy in reactions, compression of a gas, grams required to feature to an answer to succeed in desired concentration, and quantities of reactants required to succeed in a desired product. Mathematics is employed wide in chemistry and square measure fully necessary to explore vital ideas in chemistry. while not some basic arithmetic skills, these calculations, and thus chemistry itself, are going to be extraordinarily tough. However, with a basic data of a number of the arithmetic that may be utilized in your chemistry course, you'll be ready to trot out the ideas and theories of chemistry. Physics is that the understanding of the laws of nature. Physics explores primarily into mathematical ideas. We argue that adequately matching arithmetic and physics education supports a parallel evolution of mathematical understanding and its applications in physics; crucial to the development of young scientists. Basically, maths helps in modelling. Modelling in a very sense that victimisation maths we will construct models of the processes. when a model has been engineered, we have a tendency to might do several things with it. One example may be to use that model for predictions or use the model for

optimise sure method. Now, as we have a tendency to square measure progressing towards convergence of biology with alternative fields like information processing, applied science, etc., the models of biological processes can become indispensable. within the future, a lot of and a lot of biology work like genetic circuit style, population modelling, etc. are going to be done on the pc. and also, the computer code on the pc is going to be designed victimisation maths. So, in close to future, a man of science with mathematical skills are going to be in nice demand and can be in far better position to try and do inter-disciplinary analysis than his counterparts.

Biomathematics is one such branch of biology which includes analysis of data with help of mathematical models and abstractions of the living organisms to analyze the principles that rule the structure. Theoretical biology focuses a lot of on the events based on principles of theory of biology whereas mathematical biology focuses on mathematical tools to review biological systems.

VI. CONCLUSION

Mathematics may be an organized application of matter. Scientists and engineers need mathematics to do each and every task such as obtaining and studying information, recognising patterns and many more. It makes it easier for the scholars to comprehend elaborate data. Therefore, maths is sort of essential to be taught at every educational institution as it is much needed in everyday lives and is the

basis of all career options. Every single moment of our life needs information of maths. Math is significant in our world nowadays. Everybody uses arithmetic in our day to day lives, and most of the time, we have a tendency to don't even comprehend it. Without maths, our world would be missing a key part in its makeup.

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